

PREVALENCE OF IMPOSTER PHENOMENON AMONG DOCTOR OF PHYSICAL THERAPY STUDENTS AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A CROSS SECTIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17247975>

Received
05 September 2025

Accepted
16 September 2025

Published
02 October 2025

ABSTRACT

Introduction and objectives: The imposter phenomenon (IP) refers to a feeling of persistent self –doubt, a sense of intellectual fraudulence in individual despite of evident competence. This issue has been observed widely particularly in high achieving students in competitive academic environments. The main aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence of imposter phenomenon among doctor of physiotherapy students along with association of academic performance. Method: A cross-sectional study was conducted at Mohi-ud-din institute of rehabilitation sciences Mirpur AJ&K involving multiple DPT departments in Mirpur city with a sample of 242 undergraduate DPT students. The Clance Impostor phenomenon Scale (CIPS) was used to assess the presence of IP , While academic performance was measured using Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA). Data was analyzed through descriptive statistical using SPSS version 27. Results: Out of 242 participants and based on CIPS scoring, 47.9% exhibited moderate IP level, 38.4% frequent IP, 11.2% few characteristics, and 2.5% intense IP feelings .A CGPA above 3.5 was reported by 34.7% of students , while 51.7 % rated their academic performance as good. The findings showed no significant association between IP and academic performance. Conclusion: Imposter phenomenon is prevalent among doctor of physiotherapy students, with a substantial proportion experiencing moderate to frequent imposter feelings. Although there was no significant correlation found between imposter phenomenon and academic performance.

Keywords: Imposter phenomenon, Doctor of Physiotherapy students, Academic Performance, Healthcare Students, CGPA.

INTRODUCTION

In a world where success, competence, achievement are viewed as indicators of a person's abilities yet some individuals are persistent in self-doubt and an overwhelming fear of being exposed as frauds. This psychological phenomenon is called as imposter phenomenon or imposter syndrome. It's not a disease rather a psychological pattern.

The presence of imposter syndrome can lead to heightened stress, anxiety, burnout, and diminished academic or professional performance. (1) The imposter phenomenon, interchangeably referred to as Imposter Syndrome , constitutes a pervasive experience where high achieving individuals persistently doubt their intellectual

competence and attribute success to external or unstable factors such as luck, timing, or error rather than to personal ability. This construct was first conceptualized by Clance and Imes in their seminal work on accomplished women, and has since evolved into a widely examined phenomenon across diverse populations, professions and cultural contexts.(2) Common manifestations of imposter syndrome include perfectionists standards, compulsive overworking, devaluing one's achievements, fear of inadequacy or failure, and reluctance to accept positive feedback.(3) The condition is strongly interlinked with anxiety, low self-confidence, and an inconsistent sense of self, factors that can significantly compromise both mental health and occupational performance. Initially, the findings were more common in women due to the gender difference and social expectations.

IP is most commonly observed in high achieving individuals, particularly students and professionals in competitive fields such as healthcare field remains the most documented field in aspect of imposter phenomenon. As a result, IP does not only have an effect on student's well-being rather it has a great influence of patient outcome and long term professional development. Imposter Phenomenon among DPT students It is known to have effect on all different domains of medical field such as MBBS, BDS, DPT, pharmacy, nursing etc and has an impact all levels of medical training beginning with medical students and continuing during stages of transition and even in senior faculty. Some professional experience it earlier and some in later stages of life but although medical students and residents both are susceptible to IP. Imposter phenomenon exists in significant percentage of medical students 62,8% and residents with results 77.2%.(4) and appears to be peak in third year because of a transition of student from a classroom learning to clinical responsibilities. Another study concluded that this condition tend to increase pressure in final year due to transition from academic learning to increasing responsibilities in daily clinical practice.(5)

Several studies suggest that Pakistan remains the highly prevalent country in comparison of Asian countries. the Asian and middle east countries show more prevalence than north America and western Europe one For instance, research conducted in china at peiking union medical hospital found imposter syndrome significantly

more in medicals students than in residents in china. The Harvard medical school in US with 30% positive findings.(6) Jazan university in Saudia Arabia found that 24.3% of students with positive imposter syndrome findings.(7) In contrast, study conducted in Pakistan has showed 62.5% prevalence of imposter syndrome.(8) Cultural attitude and societal values play very crucial rule in developing imposter phenomenon. Cultural value put individual to feel immense pressure to succeed in academic excellence, familial reputation and high expectations.

The imposter phenomenon has significant bad influence on academic performance. Academic performance is crucial factor in student's success influencing career opportunities and professional confidence. It is influenced by various factors including motivation, self-efficacy, mental health, and external pressures.(9)some students with imposter phenomenon may still perform well academically on the other hand some student may struggle to perform due to anxiety, stress and self-doubt. Barari et al. 2024 highlight that imposter syndrome is prevalent among university students with nearly two out of five experiencing self-doubt and fear of being exposed as frauds. the study suggests that students affected by IS can negatively impact their academic performance and over all well-being.(10) Individuals with high imposter levels were more likely to adopt maladaptive behaviors such as avoiding to perform and getting engaged in self-handicapped behaviors both of which are indirectly related to poor academic performance and outcomes.(11)

Despite existence of extensive researches on imposter syndrome globally on general student population. There has been limited focus on its prevalence among doctor of physical therapy students particularly in Pakistan. Numerous studies have been conducted on both medical and non-medical students but there is no significant data emphasis on DPT students. The purpose of this study was to investigate the prevalence of the imposter phenomenon among physiotherapy students in Pakistan and to analyze its potential association with academic performance.

METHODOLOGY:

A Cross sectional study design was employed for this research. The study was conducted over a period of six months following approval from the

Institutional Committee (IRC). The research setting included various physiotherapy institutes of Mirpur AJK . For the sampling technique non probability convenient method was used. Since physiotherapy students were only the part of study so after calculating the all number of students in included departments the total population size turned out to be a 647, after that Rao soft software was used determine the sample size. The estimated size came out 242. Undergraduate physical therapy students of both gender and age from 17-25 years and Students from all semesters were added in study. Any student who was already suffering from psychological disorder except imposter phenomenon and Students who have taken semester break previously were excluded from the study. After obtaining consent from IRC committee, all the participants were recruited according to the study design that was convenience sampling method from multiple Doctor of Physical Therapy Institutes in Mirpur AJK. After applying sample inclusion and exclusion criteria we obtained written consent from the respective participants. During that process, students were instructed how to complete the questionnaire. The questionnaire were distributed to all participants in person and hard form. All the data was recorded

manually and then transferred to SPSS for the analysis. Data is securely stored and only accessible to the primary researchers.

RESULTS

Table 01 presents all the demographical profile of participants, Out of 242 sample size, the frequency and percentage of female participants was 203(83.9%) while the male participants were 39 (16.1%). The more than half of participants (57.9%) were between (20-22 years). The participants aged between (17-19 years) showed 24.8% of sample and remaining (23- 25 years) accounted for 17.4%. The sample 47.9% fell within the range of 41 to 60 showing moderate characteristics. Additionally, 38.4% scored rages from 61 to 80 showing frequent imposter feelings. The participants falling below 40 had 11.2% reporting to have few imposter characteristics while a very smaller group 2.5% had scores above 80 indicating intense imposter phenomenon. None of the participants in this study scored 20 that was minimum possible score. (Table 02) Students with fair CGPA were more likely to report frequent IP. Whereas those with average and excellent CGPA mostly reported moderate IP. (Table 03)

TABLE - 01 DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PARTICIPANTS:

VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GENDER		
Male	39	16.1%
Female	203	83.9%
AGE		
17-19	60	24.8%
20-22	140	57.9%
23-25	42	17.4%
BMI		
lower than 18.5	51	21.1%
18.5 to 25 optimal	156	64.5%
25 to upto 30 overweight	28	11.6%
30 upwards obese	7	2.9%
SEMESTERS		
First	9	3.7%
Second	57	23.6%
third	10	4.1%
fourth	38	15.7%
fifth	13	5.4%
sixth	27	11.2%
seventh	8	3.3%
Eighth	43	17.8%

Ninth	8	3.3%
Tenth	29	12.0%
CGPA		
Below 3.0	38	15.7%

Equal to 3.0	44	18.2%
Above 3.0	76	31.4%
Above 3.5	84	34.7%
IP AWARENESS		
yes	93	38.4%
No	149	61.6%

TABLE - 2 SCORING OF CIPS

CIPS	Frequency	Percentage
No IP (20 score)	0	0%
Few characteristics (Less than 40)	27	11.2%
Moderate IP (41-60 score)	116	47.9%
Frequent imposter feelings (61-80 score)	93	38.4%
Intense IP (More than 80 Intense)	6	2.5%
Total students	242	100.0%

TABLE 3: CROSS-TABULATION BETWEEN CIPS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE:

CGPA categories	Fair	Clance IP scale Scoring				Total	Chi-square test value
		<40 means few characteristics	41-60 modeate IP	61-80 frequent IP	moe than 80 intense IP		
	Average	3	20	19	2	44	
	Good	5	40	30	1	76	
	Excellent	14	43	26	1	84	
	Total	27	116	93	6	242	

DISCUSSION:

This study identified a high prevalence of the imposter phenomenon, with 88.8% of physiotherapy students reporting moderate to severe traits. This proportion is higher than the 83% reported in Slovenia (12) and also exceeds findings from a Lahore based study where MBBS students demonstrated greater prevalence than DPT students.(13) These findings suggest that Pakistani DPT students may be particularly vulnerable to imposter feelings, potentially due to sociocultural expectations, peer pressure,

Despite the high prevalence, inferential analysis demonstrated only a negative association between imposter phenomenon and academic performance. This contrasts with studies from Saudi Arabia (3) Which identified links between imposter traits and higher CGPA or perceived academic performance, as well as with the systematic review by Bravata et al, which highlighted significant adverse effects of imposter phenomenon on academic and professional outcomes.(1) Our findings therefore indicate that imposter tendencies may be present irrespective of students' perceived academic achievements. Whereas, on the contrary another previous study in medical university of Malaysia found significant association of subjective academic performance with imposter phenomenon. (14)

BMI of all the respective participants were analyzed that students with overweight BMI showing more frequent imposter characteristics than normal. Now to support our current finding or compare it with other study there is no existing literature available particularly in students with overweight BMI and their relationship with IP. As we know in this era, physical appearance and weight for an individual is very sensitive especially among young adults/students. So this raises an unexplored area for future research. Where a valuable findings can contribute to healthcare researches. Keeping in mind the cultural and societal expectations from Pakistani students where failure is seen as humiliation and parents put pressure on their children to excel in their career and to maintain the family legacy so we added another demographical question that was parental level of education as a part of information although it wasn't our objective

and our study showed no insignificant relationship with both fathers and mother level of education. The participant's response reported to have parents with different level of education majorly reporting to have bachelors level of degrees. But the recent article published in 2024 emphasized that parents with high educational background put pressure on their children that can lead to imposter phenomenon.(15)

A noteworthy trend was the higher frequency of imposter feelings among students in the transitional stage of clinical rotations 5th to 7th semesters. It is plausible that exposure to clinical practice and the accompanying responsibilities heighten self-doubt and performance-related anxiety. Similar patterns have been reported in Multan, where third year medical students displayed greater imposter traits (11), and at Jouf medical university, where first year students were more vulnerable due to the academic pressure of transition.(16)Collectively, these findings reinforce the view that imposter phenomenon intensifies during periods of academic and professional transition, underscoring the need for tailored psychological support at these stages. However, the participants in study reported to belong majorly from Mirpur city which is a small city but it was an unexplored area for research. In light of the previous finding in Kerala, India where urban and rural students were evaluated and students from rural areas showed more IP characteristic.(17)

Additional thing that has been also observed in the demographical profile is that students don't know much about imposter phenomenon term that also contributes to developing imposter phenomenon. So educating students and providing timely counselling, therapeutic interventions, self-reflection analysis to individual suffering

from IP can help to overcome although our finding is not supporting this literature but to conclude and recommend if a small city like Mirpur has raised level of results than in advanced and big cities it might will have more effect on DPT students. The ratio of both genders in study was imbalanced, females accounted more than males so for future the study can be conducted with equal distribution of females and males ratio. The next study with

the involvement of clinical psychologist can be more helpful in process of evaluation.

CONCLUSION:

Our study concluded that 88.8% of participants included in study exhibit imposter phenomenon. Among them half of the participants exhibited moderate imposter phenomenon characteristics, while a substantial portion showing frequent imposter characteristics and only small percentage of sample is experiencing intense IP. The study showed no significant association of imposter phenomenon and academic performance

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